

TECHNOLOGY OF PLANT PROTECTION FROM LOW TEMPERATURE

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Abstract

By introducing the technology of protection of plants from low temperature in addition to cryoprotectors and fertilizers, productivity is increased as a result of the effect of maintaining the number of plants and providing them with nutrients. The most favorable conditions are to study the background of cryoprotectors and potash fertilizers. Plants are very sensitive to cold during the growing season. For example, as a result of frostbite during the germination period of plants, a part of the crop can be lost. In order to increase the resistance of plants to cold, the substance that we want to use in the experiment is a cryoprotectant. In order to study the cold demand of plants, during the experiment, the level of cold resistance of the cryoprotectant substance of plants is studied. For this purpose, plant cold resistance was studied during the plant growth period.

Keywords:

Cryobiology, protector, plant, short-term low temperature, cold tolerance, thermometric observation, number of plants, productivity.

Enter. As the world's population grows, the demand for food products increases accordingly. As a result, providing the world's population with food is one of the urgent issues of today. Currently, as a result of climate change, there are unfavorable conditions for growing plants. In such a situation, it is appropriate to use substances that allow you to grow products under any conditions without any difficulties. The center of our republic, the northern agricultural products allow to solve the problem of growing tomorrow's vegetables and other agricultural crops, get high and quality crops, and make efficient use of the land. In the southern and central regions of Uzbekistan, plants are planted in late

February and early March. In recent years, as a result of sudden changes in the weather, the plants planted in March were hit by frost, and the need for food is increasing even more. In order to prevent this, it is necessary to use cryoprotectants, which increase the cold resistance of plants, to increase the cold resistance of plants. These substances prevent the formation of crystalline substances by freezing the water in the plant cell in cold weather, that is, it turns into a round shape instead of a crystal. This prevents plant cell damage. Therefore, an effective method of using cryoprotectant substances will be created in Uzbekistan. Solving the problem of growing durum wheat and corn from tomorrow's vegetable, potato and cereal crops in the central and northern regions of our republic, obtaining a high and quality harvest, making it possible to use the land efficiently and free up the area for the second crop earlier is an important agrotechnical event for agriculture. is considered Tomorrow's potatoes are planted in the southern and central regions of Uzbekistan in late February and early March. The purpose of planting at this time is that the flowering period of potatoes does not coincide with the hottest period of summer. However, long-term data shows that, due to the influence of the climate, the actual planting of tomorrow's potatoes lasts until the end of April, and the flowering period coincides with the hottest days. The yield is lower than that of potatoes planted in summer. Durum wheat is an important crop for the national economy and is considered a biological spring. Compared to winter wheat, it is resistant to low temperatures. This feature causes damage to the plant [4]. The climate conditions of the central regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan are unique and different from other regions. During the winter and warm spring days, there are many favorable temperature days and temperature changes. It has different effects on potato, durum wheat and corn. In most cases, a sharp drop in temperature is observed at the end of winter and early spring. In February, March, April, May several short-term low temperatures are observed. This situation creates unfavorable conditions for tomorrow's crop production. Sown seeds are affected by cold, although there are many hot days in February-March in the central regions.

In recent years, the field of cryobiology has developed and great achievements have been made in the field of medicine. Our scientific research uses special cryobiological substances to protect plants from cold temperatures, increase their resistance to cold, save the number of balls in the field, and reduce excess consumption costs, increasing productivity and its quality. The use of the achievements of cryobiology in farming is a promising method to introduce into

production. To the plant cell increasing the cold resistance of the tissue under the influence of these substances is the content of the scientific work [2].

Materials and methods. Polyethylene oxide (PEO-400) with 400 molecular weight, propanediol (1,2-PD) with 76 molecular weight, and polyethylene glycol (PEG-1500) with 1500 molecular weight polymer were used in our field experiments as a cryoprotectant against low temperature, and observations are made based on the methodology. In this cold protection technology, aqueous solutions of cryoprotectants are treated for a certain period of time and research is carried out on plants.

One of the main agrotechnical measures is to grow healthy lawns of the optimal thickness in order to produce a high yield of certain plant varieties planted in autumn. It is known that field germination of seeds is much lower than laboratory germination. The field fertility of seeds depends on the quality of seeds, agrotechnics, soil-climatic conditions, damage of seeds by diseases and pests, and various other factors.

Conclusions. In short, cryoprotectants and potassium fertilizers increase the plant's resistance to low temperatures. This, in turn, prevents damage from early spring and short-term cold temperatures. The thickness of the ball is maintained on the field. In addition, the protected plant grows actively due to the effective use of climate and soil conditions.

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